

Employee Development: Motivation is the key to success

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Abstract: Human nature can be very simple, yet very complex too. An understanding and appreciation of this is a prerequisite to effective people motivation in both workplace and elsewhere and therefore effective management and leadership. Employee motivation is the major part of employee development. Effective motivation enhances the employees' intrinsic sense of accomplishment, contribution, involvement, and satisfaction. A number of techniques have been discussed to develop the motivation of employees. As a guideline, there are broadly several strategies for motivation: ambition, need achievement, money, base rewards on job performance, job environment, job enlargement, interpersonal relations, recruitment procedure, training and organizational development etc. The selection of any of these measures for motivational development emphasizes on the nature of the employee to be motivated, type of task to be gained and extent of satisfying employees needs considered in any organization. Apart from the benefit and moral value of an altruistic approach to treating employees as human beings in all its form, research and observations show that well motivated employees are more productive and creative. The purpose of this article is to focus on employee development (ED) practices through employees' motivation for organizational development.

1. Introduction

There is a proverb, "you can take a horse to the water but you cannot force it to drink; it will drink only if it's thirsty" – so with the people, employees in particular, in an organization. They will do what they want to do or otherwise motivated to do. For, Motivation is the process of arousing action, sustaining the activity in progress and regulating the pattern in activity. Numerous articles are written on the motivation of employees but scientists who have studied human behavior and psychology have found that there isn't a single answer to motivating employees. Organizations are constantly looking at different ways and approaches by which they can "motivate" their employees, improve workplace morale and create better work environments. (Taleen Tchalikian, 2005)

Employee motivation is usually at a high level when the organizations, the individual objectives and values are aligned. Therefore, organizations can look at ways to collecting data about the work environment, hold focus groups and staff meetings on what they would like to see in the organization in order to improve morale and take corrective actions based on the data results.

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It is important to keep in mind the different motivational factors that work with different people. It is also important to understand that not all people are motivated by a single factor; instead they are motivated by a series of factors. These factors change during the course of time, greatly depending on the particular phase that an individual might be going through, whether it is in his personal life or career. The research has shown that some of the biggest motivation factors are the organization for which employees work, the work environment, their boss, money, the achievements they can produce when they play a specific role, recognition, power and authority, status, their peers, team and co-workers.

2. Objectives of the study

Objectives of this study would include: a. Identifying various techniques of motivation; b. Examining the impact of motivation on employee development; c. Knowing about various ways of employee development; d. Learning about various theories of motivation; e. Determining the effect of employee motivation on organizational development; f. Setting development objectives; g. Identifying learning and development opportunities; h. Identifying the behaviors relevant to work success.

3. An overview of employee development

Employee development is closely linked to the growth of a company or any organization. This is especially true for small businesses, in which employee plays a vital role in the success of the company. Employee growth has direct and indirect benefits. More knowledgeable, skilled and capable employees directly impact a company's ability to satisfy customers, resolve problems, crises, and adapt to changing market conditions.

Basically, employee development, unlike personal development, is usually coordinated by the employing organization. It can use a variety of training methods, and is usually conducted on planned basis. When companies think of employee development, they often search for training programs, educational seminars, coaching, or the latest book that might offer ideas on what employees can do to sharpen skills or strengthen expertise (**Gayle Lantz**, [http:// www.gaylelantz.com](http://www.gaylelantz.com)). However, none of these programs will be effective if the organization lacks one critical success factor: individual motivation. An individual has to want to develop himself before any employee training and development program can be successful.

Therefore, here are some tips discussed to help motivate the seemingly unmotivated and increase any organization's overall performance.

1. To target the highly motivated and strong performers. All organizations have individuals who are highly motivated. They stand out more easily. They typically like

challenges and welcome growth opportunities for themselves. To engage them in activities to help them get even better. The improved performance of the highly motivated will help raise the bar for the entire organization. Those who are less motivated will have to step up the pace.

2. To focus on the future. Rather than to concentrate on performance areas that aren't working for an individual, talk about possibilities for the future. It's easier to become energized about new possibilities than dwelling on weaknesses. To determine the positive outcome that will occur if a change/improvement is made. For example, you might say, "We can reach more buyers if you can speak more frequently to groups. What can you do to hone your presentation skills to help secure more business?" To help employees keep their eye on the goal, not their ego.

3. To open dialogue about desire. Discussions about development should be positive and ongoing -- not limited to annual performance reviews. To let the individual lead. Rather than saying, "Here are areas you need to develop," ask "What would help you build on your strengths or increase your effectiveness?" When a particular approach has been identified, ask for commitment to follow-through. To create a culture where ongoing development is expected, encouraged and rewarded at all levels.

4. To start at the top. Executives should model the commitment to growth and development that they want to see throughout the organization. After all, many problems disguised as employee development issues actually reflect leadership deficiencies of the firm or organization.

Any organizations can consider using assessments of some kind to help employees gain a more objective perspective about them. Assessments can be helpful or destructive depending on how they are used. In the end, it's all about achieving what both the employees and what the organization wants. It has to be clear about what's the most important to both (Source: <http://www.workmatters.com/>).

Employee development is not something to be checked off on a checklist. The strongest organizations make employee development an integral part of their culture and strategies for success through motivation. They constantly seek new and innovate ways to engage their people in development opportunities to achieve best results.

4. Motivation: Theory and practice

The term "**Motivation**" can be traced to the Latin word 'movere', which means to move. It is moving people to perform something. It is a process of arousing action, sustaining the activity in progress and regulating the pattern in the activity. Motivation attempts to

influence or cause certain behavior. It is the set of forces that cause people to behave in certain ways. Motivation is the way in which drives or needs direct a person's behavior towards a goal. It points to the final strength of action tendency, which is experienced by the person as in "I want to". However, it is a process involving a few steps. It begins with needs or a deficiency. People have needs although the number of needs is limited. Needs are essential for survival. An unfulfilled or unsatisfied internal need creates tension that stimulates drives within the individual. We can say that motivated employees are in a state of tension. To relieve this tension, they exert effort. These drives generate a search behavior towards achieving goals, which will satisfy need and finally result in satisfaction or reduction of tension. resulting from behavior. Motivation can be seen as a need-satisfying process. The motivation process is shown in the following way:

Source: *Human Resources management*, Decenzo, 4th Edition, 2002, Singapore

Motivation induces employees to act in a desired manner. It concerns the level of effort put forth to pursue specific goals. It is the willingness to exert high levels of effort to organizational goals, conditioned by the effort's ability to satisfy some individual need (*Decenzo and Robbins, 1999*). There are three elements in this definition: effort, organizational goal and needs. When someone motivated, he puts more effort. Individual needs must be compatible and consistent with the organizational goals.

There are various theories regarding human nature in general and motivation in particular. The practical aspects of the motivation in the workplace and the research that have been undertaken in this field, notably by Douglas McGregor (theory y), Fredrick Herzberg (two factor motivation hygiene theory,) Abraham Maslow (theory Z, hierarchy of needs), and David McClelland (achievement motivation) etc. Here an attempt is made to discuss the above mentioned theories in the following:

Douglas McGregor (theory y)

In the Human Side of Enterprise, published in 1960, Douglas McGregor contrasted two sets of assumptions about workers' attitudes to work and responsibility and commonly known as Theory X and Theory Y.

These two sets of assumptions are fundamentally different. Theory X is pessimistic, static, and rigid. In contrast Theory Y is optimistic, dynamic and flexible, with an emphasis of self-direction. Theory X assumes that lower order needs dominate employees and theory Y assumes that higher order needs dominate. The traditional assumptions about the nature of people or employees, according to **Theory Y** :

- Enjoy work and do not want to avoid it.
- Want to attain organizational goals through self-directed behavior.
- Will accept responsibility.
- Have initiative and can be creative in solving organizational problem.

Theory X assumes that lower order needs dominate employees and theory Y assumes that higher order needs dominant.

Fredrick Herzberg (two factor motivation hygiene theory)

Herzberg, a social psychologist, proposed the motivation-hygiene theory based on satisfaction. He extended the work of Maslow and developed a specific content theory of work motivation. His theory played a major role in managerial motivation. He surveyed a group of respondents, asking them to describe when they felt good or bad about their jobs. He used the critical incident method of obtaining data for analysis. He found that entirely two different sets of factors were associated with the two kinds of feelings about work. One set of factors, Herzberg called hygiene factors. These factors are associated with job context.

The hygiene factors include salary, job security, personal life, working condition, status, interpersonal relations, and technical supervision and company policies. These factors do not give positive satisfaction but their absence will cause dissatisfaction, and they cannot motivate an employee. These factors are essential to avoiding or preventing job dissatisfaction but do not lead to satisfaction.

Herzberg described the second set of factors as motivating factors. They include achievement, recognition, autonomy, challenging work advancement and growth in the job. These factors are associated with job content. Their existence will produce feelings of satisfaction or no satisfaction. These are intrinsic factors (Herzberg's two factor theory):

A) Motivational Factors
Work itself, Achievement, Possibility of growth, Responsibility, Advancement, Recognition.
B) Maintenance Factors :
Status, Relations with supervisors, Peer relations, Relations with subordinates, Quality of supervision, Company policies, Administration, Job security, Conditions, Pay.

Abraham Maslow (theory Z, hierarchy of needs)

Abraham Maslow has developed the need hierarchy theory of motivation. Need hierarchies assume that people have different needs that can be arranged in a hierarchy of importance. He proposes that human needs are not of equal strength. He saw human needs in the form of hierarchy, ascending from the lowest to the highest. He argued that people are motivated to satisfy five need levels. These are:

- Physiological (need for food, shelter, sleep, sex, and other bodily needs),
- Safety (job ,and financial security),
- Social (friendship or interaction with others),
- Esteem (high status, recognition, autonomy, self respect),
- Self-actualization (full use of potentials, able to be creative, independence, total self-direction).

Maslow separated the five needs into higher and lower order needs. Physiological and safety needs were described, as lower order needs. They are similar to primary needs. Social, esteem and self-actualization as higher order needs. Higher order needs are satisfied internally and the lower order needs are satisfied externally.

Interpretation of the hierarchy of needs

The concept of hierarchy of needs has two consequences. Firstly, unless and until a lower need is satisfied, higher order needs do not motivate. In other words, as the lower order needs are reasonably satisfied, a person places more emphasis on the higher order needs. Higher needs emerge as lower needs are fulfilled or satisfied. Secondly, once a need is satisfied, it no longer motivates. A fully satisfied need would not be a strong motivator. Only unmet needs motivate. So an effective manager is one who can identify and accept employee needs and recognize that needs may differ among employees.

David McClelland (achievement motivation)

David McClelland has identified the following three basic needs or drives within individuals:

Needs for achievement : People who spend time thinking about how they can improve on their work, who wonder how they might accomplish something that is valuable, and who derive great satisfaction from striving to do good work are considered to have a high need for achievement. McClelland conducted studies and indicated strong positive relationship between high need for achievement and high level of job performance and executive success. He offered the following reasons why people with strong need for achievement show such behavioral characteristics.

- They like situations, in which they can assume personal responsibility for solving problems.
- They tend to set moderate, realistic achievement goals and take calculated risks.
- They want concrete feedback on how they are doing.

Need for affiliation : Many people spend much of their time thinking about developing warm, friendly, personal relationships with others in the organization. They have a high need for affiliation and usually are more sensitive to other's feelings, seek to establish friendly relationships in groups by being agreeable and supportive of ideas and look for jobs with a pleasant social environment that is conducive to personal interaction. Personnel employees, teachers, nurses, counselors and many government employees typically have high need for affiliation.

Need for power : People who spend most of their time thinking about the influence and control they have over others and how they can use this influence to change people's behavior, gain authority and status and dominate decisions have a high need for power. Their needs are satisfied by manipulating and controlling others. Individuals with this need usually seek positions of leadership in organizations, are articulate, sometimes argumentative, forceful, and demanding, and not infrequently are hardheaded.

5. The importance of employee motivation at work place

In an organization or any work place the job of an employer is to get things done through the employees. To do this he should be able to motivate employees. Effective motivation enhances the employees' accomplishment in performance, and improvement in skills. To perform effectively, one should be obviously motivated or driven to work, for motivation is a skill, which can and must be learnt. This is essential for any business to survive and succeed. As performance at workplace is to be considered to be function of ability and motivation, thus:

- Job performance = f (ability) (motivation)

(Source: "Management: A Global Perspectives", Heinz Wehrich and Harold Koontz, 2002)

Ability gradually depends on education, experience and training and its progress is a lengthy process. On the other hand, motivation can be improved quickly. There are many options and an employer may not understand where to begin. As a guideline, there are several strategies for motivation.

- a. Affirmative reinforcement
- b. Effective rules and regulations
- c. Treating people fairly
- d. Satisfying employees needs
- e. Setting work related goals
- f. Restructuring jobs
- g. Base rewards on job performance

These are the basic strategies, although situation might vary from one workplace to another. Essentially, there is a distance between an individual actual state and some desired state and an employer or a manager could minimize the gap. As Motivation, is, in effect, a means to reduce and manipulate the gap. It is inducing others in a specific way towards goals specially directed by the motivator. Naturally, these goals as also the motivation system must conform to the policies of the organization. The motivational system must be tailored to the situation and to the organization.

In one of the most elaborate studies on employee motivation, involving 31,000 men and 13,000 women, the Minneapolis Gas company surveyed what their potential employees desire the most from a job. The study was carried out during a 20-year period from 1945 to 1965 and was quite revealing. The ratings for the various factors differed only slightly between men and women, but both group considered security as the highest rated factor. The next three factors are:

- a. Advancement
- b. Type of work
- c. Company-proud to work for

It is a matter of surprise; factors such as pay, benefits and working conditions were given a low rating by both groups. So after all, and contrary to common belief, money is not the prime motivator. (Though this should not be regarded as a signal to reward employees poorly or unfairly.)

Understanding employee's motivation is a key competency to being an effective leader or manager. There isn't a one off formula or black or white answer to motivating employees. In order to promote regular communication and feedback between employees and employers, employee motivation is recommended. However, we assume that three things generally determine employees' development at workplace: motivation (the desire to do the job), ability (the capability to do the job), and the work environment (the resources needed to do the job). Motivation is a general term applying to the entire class of drives, desires, needs, wishes and similar forces. To say that managers motivate their subordinates is to say that they do those things which they hope will satisfy these drives and desires and induce the subordinates to act in a desired a manner. Human motives are based on needs, whether consciously or subconsciously felt. Naturally these needs vary in intensity and over time among different individuals.

6. Objectives of employee development through motivation

Employee development can lead to more knowledgeable and skilled employees. This can give an organization a competitive advantage. With highly trained workforce a company can adapt quickly to changes in markets, solve problems and crisis and provide greater customer service. Performance appraisal can help employers and employees where employee training and development is needed. Performance appraisal can make the need for training more pressing and relevant by linking it clearly to performance outcomes and future career aspirations, allowing an organization to map and develop plans to identify individuals and areas in need of development. (Associates, 2007)

An organization can then provide courses for individuals in these areas and for those who need further training (BNET, 2006). They can also pay for academic courses, which will help develop individuals, increase motivation and can provide advantages to the organization in gaining expertise in emerging technologies and markets. (BNET, 2006).

Every business and work process eventually requires that people make decisions to do the right thing. For employees to act appropriately there must be employee motivation that is a natural growth from employee development. As human beings we are all created with a free will and the capability to make decisions. When employees are not making the correct decisions, no matter how well the process or system, problems will soon develop. Active employee development will help create the environment where employee motivation can develop more of these decisions beneficial to any organization.

Improvements in productivity of 25% to 50% have been demonstrated when employers are willing to engage their employee and create an environment where employee motivation is the norm, not the exception. (Adam Associates, 2007).

Even the best training /development programs cannot assure that all employees will get involved. One of the prime jobs of an organization is to create the climate and the systems for employee motivation. Organizations need empowered employees involved from the neck up and not just from the neck down. This is not to say that all will choose to do so. The obligation is to provide the opportunity and the means. It is then the duty of the employee to take advantage of the employee development opportunity. Most employees when they believe in and trust their organization will leap at the opportunity to make higher-level contributions to the organization. (Adams Associates, 2007)

Employee development is a technique to assess and develops employees throughout an organization while motivation, can enhance the effectiveness of the employees. Ways to encourage employee development in an organization the following points should be adapted by a company or an organization (BNET, 2006):

- **Support employee training programs**

This involves initial training when an employee first starts with a company and ongoing training programs, which encourage employees to participate in problem solving groups and in the initial training process. More experienced employees can teach new employees valuable ways to deal with the problems, while they themselves can learn about new changes in processes while they happen.

- **Tuition reimbursement**

Encourage employees to participate in education by funding outside courses. This is advantageous to a company, as they will have trained staff in emerging technologies, saving them money on outside consultants.

- **Emphasize and encourage development**

Using performance appraisals as a means to communicate expectations can increase motivation by focusing employees, and can also help encourage personal development and increase motivation.

- **Recognize and reward employee growth**

Promotions, rewards and praise are all ways to employee development. Management should constantly encourage further development by introducing incentives for individuals who are highly motivated to self-development

• Promote from within

Companies need to show employees that self-development is worthwhile by advertising opportunities and promoting internally. This will show employees that there is room to progress within a company.

7. The practical strategies for motivation development

“Your contribution is highly valued, your quality of life matters to the organization,” such an effective motivational appreciation enhances the employee’s intrinsic sense of accomplishment, contribution, involvement and satisfaction. Rewards that facilitate this usually relate to the mission and values of the organization. (Self-Actualization and Self-esteem are the highest order of Incentive: F.Hudetz: <http://beysterinstitute.org/resrc/lib/articles/hudetz.html>). In the regard, here an attempt is made to discuss some of the strategies through which to develop the motivation of employees. These are: ambition as method of bringing about self-motivation, building up the need to achieve, money working as motivator, improving the work environment, making the job meaningful to the individual by enlarging its context, using the knowledge of results of own performance, improving the interpersonal relation in the organization, providing periodic training as required for performing a job, improving the procedure of recruitment based on job specifications, and finally ,by bringing about the change in the administrative culture. The utility of a particular method depends upon the goal to be achieved, the type of person involved and the nature of the work situation.

A. Ambition: Knowledge is the goal one sets for oneself (expectation) is important for the true appraisal of the efficacy of one’s behavior and for the understanding of one’s reaction to environmental deprivation. The level of ambition provides opportunities for an individual to set his own goals in the assigned task and to obtain feedback regarding his achievement or non-achievement. This feedback helps to build up one’s level of self-motivation.

The relation between expectation and achievement has recently come to the fore under the general title of ambition. Achievements for many of us are not equal to expectations. Our culture places a premium “on getting ahead”, “on being a success,” “on making lots of money” and such positive values. This socio cultural standards of expectations creates a desire among individual to aspire for a certain levels of achievement, which for many may seem to be the remote possibility.

B. Need achievement: Need achievement defined by Murray (1938) as the need, “to work at something important with energy and persistence. To strive to accomplish something creditable. To get ahead in business, to persuade or lead a group to create something .Ambition manifested in action (Murray, 1943). Later it was extensively studied

by McClelland, who conceive it as involving a competition with a standard of excellence (McClelland et al. 1953). It gets expressed in terms of (i) affective concern over goal attainment, (ii) winning or doing well being the primary concern, (iii) meeting a self-imposed requirement of a good performance.

Achievement motivation can therefore be defined as the striving to increase or to keep as high as possible, one's own capacity in all activities. It was found in studies of entrepreneurial behavior that high levels of achievement motivation lead to innovativeness, risk taking and business success and it has been found that a person with high need to achieve tend to (a) seek and assume high degrees of personal responsibility, (b) take calculated risks, (c) set challenging but realistic goals for themselves, (d) develop comprehensive plans to help them attain their goals; (e) seek and use concrete; (f) measurable feedback of the results of their actions; seek out business opportunities where their desires to achieve will not be hindered (Stringer, 1966)

C. Money as a motivator

Money has often more than monetary value. It has also social value. It is a social medium of exchange. It can also mean status or power. Many people in Bangladesh were engaged in insider trading that resulted in huge personal profit. Classical management thinkers and scholars like Taylor, Pollock have tended to place money high on the scale of motivators. They consider employees as economic men who are only motivated by money. They assumed that economic gain was every one's primary motivation. They designed reward systems for encouraging high performance by workers and managers. Money is a motivator if it fulfills at least three conditions.

- a) Money, as money, is likely, to be more important to people who do yet meet their monetary needs. The money needs of some people are very urgent. Money is an urgent means of achieving a minimum standard of living. Money is important because of goods and services that it will purchase. This is the economic value of money. For some people money will always be of utmost importance, while for others it may never be.
- b) It is quite true that in most kinds of organizations, money is used as a means of attracting and holding qualified people. This is why organizations make their wages and salaries competitive within their industry. Katz and Khan (1976) maintains that the money reward must be perceived as fair and equitable by the majority organizational members, even those who will never seek the extra income. This is clearly explained by J. Stacy Adams (1983) in the equity theory of motivation.
- c) The money must be perceived as directly related to the required extra performance and must be received immediately upon completion.

d) It is almost certainly true that money can motivate only when prospective payment is large relative to a person's income. But employees differ in the amount of money they want. Behavioral scientists like Elton Mayo, on the other hand, tend to place money low. They give arguments against money as a motivator. Mayo and his associates found that better physical facilities or increased economic benefits in it were not sufficient motivators in increasing productivity.

There are many non-financial incentives such as employee satisfaction, morale, motivation interpersonal relationships, effective supervision, and group dynamics might increase productivity. These social needs are more important than money in motivating employees.

In reality, however, it may be more advantageous not to view money as the supreme motivator may, but as one of the many factors in the work environment that affects employee motivation. Even though money is not the only motivating force, it has been and will continue to be an important one. Money can be a motivator but not to the exclusion of other factors, including the job itself.

D. Job environment

The motivation, potential for development, capacity for assuming responsibility, readiness to direct behavior towards achievement of the goals prescribed are all presenting the incumbents of an organization. It is, therefore, its responsibility to make it possible for them to recognize and develop these characteristics. The only emphasis is to provide opportunities for the realization of the self actualization need which bolsters one's inner talent in order to view job as a challenge.

This job aspect has been found to contribute to a great deal for one's job satisfaction. The stresses and strains under which one has to carry out one's job the pressure from the higher officials on the one hand and the people or people representatives on the other create a strain on the individual, unless one has adequate personality.

E. Job enlargement

It has been argued that when a job is structured in such a way that intrinsic rewards appear to result from good performance, the job itself can be a very effective motivation. Job content is the critical determinant of whether employees believe that good performance on the job leads to feelings of accomplishment growth and self esteem. The individual must feel that he has a high degree of self control over defining the means of achieving them. It is prescribed that enlargement is more likely to lead to increased quality of job performance. Job enlargement of the development officials is to be undertaken in such a way that their role in development is made crucial to increase his intrinsic motivation.

F. Job performance

Level of performance is a constantly increasing function of the amount of motivation. There is considerable evidence that performance increases with an increase in the reward offered for successful performance. So, attempts should be made to keep motivation of the personnel at a reasonable level, so that their performance is maintained at desired levels. This could be done through financial and non financial incentives.

Interpersonal relations

Motivation for work can be improved if the work situation provides for healthy interpersonal relations. The social nature of man gives rise to certain interpersonal relations. The social nature of man gives rise to certain interpersonal needs which he must satisfy to some degree while avoiding threats to him, although each individual has different intensities of needs and different mechanism for handling them.

Direction and control have not been found to be effective as motivators of behavior. Better human relations in terms of acceptance of each others, roles and its expectations, a clear understanding of the plan of the organization in terms of its objectives may aid the motivation process.

Training

Training indirectly facilitates the growth of motivation in the directed direction. The emphasis in the training should be to change the attitudes than simply an exercise of information giving. The objective of training should be to change the ways of doing things, procedures and practices.

Recruitment procedure

It goes without saying that one of the reasons for the lack of motivation may be that a person on the job may not be suited to it. To be a development official, one needs to have certain personality attributes like (i) abstract intelligence through which it would be possible for the incumbent to visualize the consequences of his action and help in the decision making process, (ii) Social perception-an awareness of the feeling opinions and attributes of others in the group to enable him to know what others think, (iii) emotional stability –capacity to view the situation experiences objectively without giving rise to irrational behavior. Apart from this, the following qualities have been found to be present to a greater extent among leaders in a variety of situations, intelligence, adjustment, self-confidence and empathy.

Organizational development

Organizational development is a process that attempts to create an organizational climate based on behavioral science to diagnosing and remedy its inadequacies. It is a complex strategy to change the beliefs, attitudes, values and structure and organization so that they can better adapt to new technologies and challenges. The commonly sought adjectives of organization development are: (i) Improvement in interpersonal competence (ii) shift in values so that human factors and feeling come to be considered as legitimate, (iii) development of increased understanding between and within working groups in order to reduce tensions, (iv) development of more effective team management : the capacity of functioning groups to work more effectively; and (V) development of better methods of conflicts resolutions (Bennis, 1969). Rather than the usual methods which rely on mainly suppression, compromise, and unprincipled power, more rational of methods of conflict resolution are sought. More specifically, the goal is to improve communication, secure more effective participation from subordinates in problem solving and more in the direction of more openness, feedback and support.

8. Conclusion

The measures discussed for motivation so far for motivation development, has potential not only motivating key personnel in an organization but also sustaining the improved level of motivation. Motivation is the reason a person does what he does. Of all the resources available for the development of any organization, the human resource is clearly the most significant, but also the most difficult to manage. Excellence can only be achieved through excellent performance of each employee, rather than by the high-pitched performance of a few individuals. And motivation is, undoubtedly, the key. It is what drives any person or employee in organization to accomplish a task or goal and it is what keeps everyone working towards that destination.

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